
Workflows Galaxy

Progress of the β version release

Julie Lao, Romain Dallet, Kenzo-Hugo Hillion, Alix de Thoisy, Pierre Marin &
Fabien Mareuil

Genomic pipeline for ABR gene detection

Detail of each step of the genomic workflow

Tools behind each step of the genomic workflow

